

THE CRITICAL FACTORS AND PERSISTENT CHALLENGES IN ENHANCING THE EFFECTIVE DEPLOYMENT OF HUMAN CAPITAL

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In the context of New Uzbekistan, the system of vocational training is being continuously improved to meet the current demands and needs of enterprises for the professional potential of personnel. Specifically, "in our country, consistent efforts are being made to increase the well-being of the population, especially young people, through the creation of new jobs and active support for entrepreneurial initiatives. Additionally, addressing the tasks in this area necessitates creating an effective system for training highly skilled workers, taking into account the needs of the labor market, including the requirements of large enterprises and clusters being established locally". In resolving this task, priority is given to enhancing the effectiveness of reforms in the education system.

According to current legislation in the country, enhancing the level of professional training of personnel is aimed at preparing individuals for lifelong learning based on the real demand for personnel in the labor market, employer proposals, and the principle of "Education throughout life." This approach takes into account the development prospects and priority tasks of the economy, as well as modern technical and technological trends. It is assessed as a professional education system. In this system, middle-level personnel are trained with the goal of meeting labor market needs, including competitive personnel for small business and private entrepreneurship entities, by introducing stages of professional education. Additionally, it aims to fulfill the educational needs of individuals of various ages based on the principle of "Education throughout life."

Additionally, consistent reforms are being systematically implemented in our country to provide professional education services to the population, improve the system of training mid-level personnel, and ensure their effective employment. Specifically, in accordance with the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5052 dated May 24, 2017, "On Measures for Further Improving State Policy in the Field of Employment and Radically Enhancing the Efficiency of Labor Authorities," the Ministry of Labor and Social

Protection of the Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan was reorganized into the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Currently, the education programs aimed at enhancing personnel capacity in the country are not fully aligned with UNESCO's "International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) levels." This lack of alignment not only hinders the complete implementation of Uzbekistan's personnel qualification system in practice but also results in the professional qualifications of trained personnel in the education system not sufficiently meeting the requirements set by employers. Consequently, this negatively impacts the effectiveness of enterprises' utilization of personnel potential.

According to research conducted by the World Bank Group on youth employment issues and potential solutions in Uzbekistan, the country has 18 million people under the age of 29, the highest figure compared to other countries in the Europe and Central Asia region. Data indicates that 26.4% of young people aged 16-29 are not engaged in employment, education, or professional training, with 5% of those aged 15-24 and 4% of those aged 25-29 classified as "discouraged" youth. Among Central Asian countries, Uzbekistan has a relatively high rate of young people facing "discouragement" due to challenges in finding suitable employment, with this indicator averaging around 2.5% in neighboring countries.

The working-age population in the country is expected to grow by 12% over the next decade, reaching its peak by 2045. Analysis indicates that in 2020, nearly 535,000 young people in Uzbekistan graduated from vocational colleges and higher education institutions. Approximately 5.5% of individuals aged 16 and above in Uzbekistan are international labor migrants, with around 90% of them being men. The primary host countries for Uzbek labor migrants are Russia, Kazakhstan, and Turkey, with the majority of migrants being between the ages of 25-34. According to research by World Bank experts on youth employment in Uzbekistan, the main challenges in ensuring youth employment include a shortage of jobs in rural areas, weak demand for labor, high levels of informal employment, and low wages.

In enhancing the efficiency of utilizing the country's human capital, priority is given to reforms aimed at expanding the involvement of economic sectors and industries in improving the quality of training highly educated specialists. Despite ongoing reforms, there remain "gaps between higher education, science, and production in the country, with insufficient integration among them. Research institutions are not adequately involved in the personnel training

process within higher education, and scientific research is conducted without fully considering the actual needs of economic sectors. The lack of systematic training of highly qualified scientific and academic personnel is leading to a decline in the scientific potential of higher education institutions."

As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized, "In an environment where competition in the global market is increasingly intense, enhancing the efficiency of the personnel training system by raising the quality of education and scientific potential plays a crucial role in ensuring the country's economic development." Therefore, in the context of New Uzbekistan, priority is given to implementing educational programs focused on training mid-level personnel and highly educated specialists who meet the professional requirements of enterprises. Additionally, in recent years, enterprises across national economic sectors have increasingly implemented programs for training, vocational education, and skill enhancement for their employees. In our view, strengthening the integrative relationship between "education, science, and production" in the coming years will not only improve the human capital potential but also positively impact the efficiency of its utilization.

Literature:

1. Воробьев А.Д., Жданов С.Б., Кузмина Ю.А. Стратегическое управление персоналом // Управление персоналом, № 15, 2014. – с. 48-53.
2. Зарубина Т.А. "Кадровый потенциал" и "трудоустройство": различия в определении понятий // Аллея науки. – 2017. – № 8 (1). – с. 218-221.
3. Ильченко С.В. Компетентностный подход в управлении человеческими ресурсами организации // Вестник экспериментального образования: научно-методический электронный журнал. № 2. 2015. – с. 7-13.
4. Нонака И., Такеучи Х. Компания – создатель знания. Зарождение и развитие инноваций в японских фирмах. – М.: ЗАО "Олим-Бизнес", 2003. – 384 с.
5. Рябчук П.Г., Федерова К.А., Апухтин А.С., Плужникова И.И. Анализ современных методик оценки кадрового потенциала // Экономика труда. № 9, 2017. – с. 1-18.
6. Future of Jobs Report 2023: Insight report. World Economic Forum (WEF). May 2023. pp. 296. URL: https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Future_of_Jobs_2023.pdf
7. Honorati, Maddalena Marguerie, Alicia Charlena. Youth Employment in Uzbekistan: Opportunities and Challenges. Washington, D.C. : World Bank Group.

September – 2021. p. 89.

<https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documentdetail/235891634705237783/youth-employment-in-uzbekistanopportunities-and-challenges>

8. O*NET Resource Center. <https://www.onetcenter.org/overview.html>.

9. Кибанова А.Я. Управление деловой карьерой, служебно-профессиональным продвижением и кадровым резервом: Учебно-практическое руководство. – М.: Проспект, 2014. – 64 с.

10. Кузнецова И.В. Управление кадровым потенциалом в промышленности. // дисс. ... к.э.н. Казань, 2002 – с. 66.

11. Q.H. Abdurahmonov, Sh.R. Xolmo‘minov, A.B. Hayitov, A.M. Akbarov – Personalni boshqarish. (O‘quv qo‘llanma) – T.: 2004. – 160 bet.

12. Дустова , А. К. (2023). Методы оценки кадрового потенциала в организациях на примере зарубежного опыта // Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(17 SPECIAL), 43–47. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/5139>.

13. Дустова А. К. Основные направления развитие кадрового потенциала предприятия //“Iqtisodiy tadqiqotlarga asoslangan oliy malumotli iqtisodchi kadrlarni tayorlash. – С. 496.

